

The Partners

Consortium
15 Early stage researchers (ESRs) working with 4 industrial and 5 academic partners from 6 EU countries.

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5G STEP FWD

5G System Technological Enhancements
Provided by Fiber Wireless Deployments

Main Objectives

The essence of 5G STEP FWD is based on applying ultra dense wavelength division multiplexing (UD-WDM) in the radio access network (RAN) with advanced beamforming methods for wireless transmission of 5G signals to a large numbers of users within small-cells.

The developed solutions will be seamlessly integrated into the already existing and next generation passive optical networks (PON) and will feature full support for software defined networking (SDN) and network function virtualization (NFV) based on state of the art machine learning techniques. 5G STEP FWD will pave a feasible and dynamic path towards 5G wireless communications with a 1000 fold increase in capacity, connectivity for over 1 billion users, ultra low latency (<10ms) and secure flexible network software programming.

Project Facts

5G STEP FWD is a European international training network (ITN) project led by Iquadrat Informática S. L. The project concentrates the efforts of 9 partners from both academia and industry stemming from 6 different countries to cope with the major challenges of the 5G cellular networks and develop technologies enabling a cost effective 5G infrastructure with vastly improved performance while reducing power consumption.

Duration:
48 Months: June 2017 – May 2021

Budget:
€3.8 M from the European Commission under the Horizon 2020 programme

Expected Impact and Research Challenges

- * 5G STEP FWD develops an efficient and pragmatic approach for a 5G fronthaul and backhaul network capable of addressing the high capacity and flexibility requirements imposed by the advanced 5G services.
- * The solution provided by 5G STEP FWD offers exceptional characteristics whose impacts include the analysis of multiple challenges in three research areas that will be investigated by 15 ESRs hosted by the 9 partners of the consortium.

Wireless Challenges

- ◆ Mathematical modeling and assessment of mm-wave networks with improved performance and efficiency.
- ◆ Cost efficient processes for optimal placement of radio cloud centers maximizing the connectivity and resource sharing among end users.
- ◆ Analysis of backhaul systems enhancing the performance of small base stations.
- ◆ Synthesis of an antenna array prototype for mmWave communications with highly directional beamforming.

Optical Challenges

- ◆ Optimized communicational and computational resource allocation based on sophisticated traffic flows.
- ◆ Dynamic traffic steering in SDN/NFV integration with new management and orchestration mechanisms.
- ◆ UDWDM-PON architecture modeling and design employing novel analytical tools based on the upgrade of existing PON infrastructure with minimal new-fiber installation.
- ◆ Design and fabrication of photonic integrated PON transceivers.

Optical-Wireless Challenges

- ◆ Development of algorithms for fronthaul dynamic slicing implemented on a unified SDN control plane in the converged network.
- ◆ Novel modulation techniques enabling the hybrid transmission of signals within the converged networks.
- ◆ Implementation of photonic-wireless links accommodating multiple user channels at different frequency bands aggregated over the same optical channel.

Proposed Network Architecture

Backhaul Network

Centralized reconfigurable infrastructure by means of SDN and NFV orchestration.

Fronthaul Network

Advanced interface between the optical network and the radiating elements of 5G base stations based on radio over fiber techniques.

Wireless Network

Support on multiple vertical use cases such as autonomus driving, robotics and e-health.

